

IDENTIFICATION OF THE VISCOELASTIC CONSTITUTIVE EQUATIONS OF FLAX FIBRE REINFORCED LAMINATES BY VIBRATION ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Experimental and numerical approaches to identify the viscoelastic properties of flax fibre reinforced epoxy composite laminates are proposed in this study. The method used consisted the identification of the evolutions of both loss factor and stiffness through the use of the frequency responses. Several free-free symmetrically guided beams were excited on the dynamic range of 10 to 4000 Hz with a swept sine excitation focused around their first's modes. A fractional derivative Zener model was used to predict the behaviour of on-axis ply complex moduli. The modified ply constitutive law was then implemented in Classical Lamination Theory (CLT) calculation routine. The properties of the laminates were predicted on a large frequency bandwidth. Simulation and experimentation on $[\pm 60]_s$ and $[0/90]_s$ laminates have validated the prediction of the linear viscoelastic properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Structural parts of land vehicles are subjected to dynamic loads. Excitations coming from the powertrain, road irregularities and aerodynamic flows cause mechanical vibration in the car-body. Consequently, acoustic and vibration comfort inside vehicles are decreased. Plant fibres reinforced polymer exhibit interesting dissipative mechanical behaviour. Compared to conventional composite materials, flax fibre reinforced polymer damping performance can be twice or three times larger than respectively glass and carbon fibre reinforced composites [1-3].

The damping in undamaged composite can be induced by several micro-scale mechanisms, such as the viscoelastic strain of matrix and/or fibres, frictions at matrix-fibre interface, also at fibre bundle interface in the case of composites reinforced by plant fibres. Meso-scale mechanisms, such as layer orientation, interlaminar effect, and vibration coupling can also affect the laminate dissipation of energy.

Several authors [6-12] have noticed that dissipative properties of polymer matrix composite depend on frequency. This dependence to frequency can be predicted with a viscoelastic analysis. Numerous studies, related to the time-dependence of mechanical properties of polymer matrix composite are available in the literature [13-16]. Crane and Gillespie [12] have proposed an approach similar to the CLT theory to predict laminate properties frequency dependence. Using complex moduli and assuming that storage moduli are frequency independent, this approach remained not suitable for temporal analysis. The present study aims at presenting a model which calculates both stiffness moduli and loss factors depending on frequency. Based on linear viscoelasticity theory, this approach is consistent in both temporal and frequency analyses.

2 LINEAR VISCOELASTIC MODEL

The mechanical energy is totally or partly restored during the unloading stage depending on the material behaviour. In viscoelastic materials, this delay, due to inner rearrangements, is in the range of the experiment duration. The stress depends on the strain history [17]. For small strains, the dependence

to time or frequency can be expressed by linear differential equations or by convolution integrals. The fractional derivative Zener model (figure 1) has been used by many authors to describe the viscoelastic behaviour [18]. This model is mathematically described by Eq. 1.

$$\sigma(t) + \left(\frac{\mu}{E_2}\right)^\alpha D^\alpha[\sigma(t)] = E_1 \varepsilon(t) + (E_1 + E_2) \left(\frac{\mu}{E_2}\right)^\alpha D^\alpha[\varepsilon(t)] \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: Fractional derivative Zener model.

σ , ε , t and α are respectively the stress, strain, time and the order fractional derivative operator ($0 < \alpha < 1$). D is a fractional derivative operator. E_1 , E_2 and μ are the material stiffness and viscosity, mentioned in figure 1. In the case of a steady state harmonic excitation, the complex modulus is written in Eq. 2. It is possible to modify Eq. 2 to Eq. 3

$$E^*(\omega) = \frac{\sigma^*(\omega)}{\varepsilon^*(\omega)} = \frac{E_1 + (E_1 + E_2) \left(j\omega \left(\frac{\mu}{E_2} \right)^\alpha \right)}{1 + \left(j\omega \left(\frac{\mu}{E_2} \right)^\alpha \right)} \quad (2)$$

$$E^*(\omega) = E'(\omega) + jE''(\omega) = E'(\omega)[1 + j\eta(\omega)] \quad (3)$$

j is the imaginary unit ($j^2 = -1$), ω the angular frequency and $E'(\omega)$ the real part of the complex modulus which gives the elastic behaviour of the specimen, also called storage modulus. The imaginary part ($E''(\omega)$) is called loss modulus and represents the viscous or damping behaviour of the tested material. $\eta(\omega) = E''(\omega) / E'(\omega)$ represents the material loss factor. According to the constitutive Eq. 1, E' and η are expressed in Eq. 4 and 5. $\Re[E^*(\omega)]$ and $\Im[E^*(\omega)]$ are real and imaginary parts of $E^*(\omega)$.

$$E'(\omega) = \Re[E^*(\omega)] = E_1 \frac{1 + \left(\frac{E_1 + E_2}{E_1} + 1 \right) \cos\left(\frac{\alpha\pi}{2}\right) \left(\frac{\mu}{E_2} \omega \right)^\alpha + \frac{E_1 + E_2}{E_1} \left(\frac{\mu}{E_2} \omega \right)^{2\alpha}}{1 + 2 \cos\left(\frac{\alpha\pi}{2}\right) \left(\frac{\mu}{E_2} \omega \right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{\mu}{E_2} \omega \right)^\alpha} \quad (4)$$

$$\eta(\omega) = \frac{\Im[E^*(\omega)]}{\Re[E^*(\omega)]} = \frac{\left(\frac{E_1 + E_2}{E_1} - 1 \right) \sin\left(\frac{\alpha\pi}{2}\right) \left(\frac{\mu}{E_2} \omega \right)^\alpha}{1 + \left(\frac{E_1 + E_2}{E_1} + 1 \right) \cos\left(\frac{\alpha\pi}{2}\right) \left(\frac{\mu}{E_2} \omega \right)^\alpha + \frac{E_1 + E_2}{E_1} \left(\frac{\mu}{E_2} \omega \right)^{2\alpha}} \quad (5)$$

3 CLASSICAL LAMINATE THEORY IN VISCOELASTICITY

The CLT calculates the elastic properties of the laminate based on the elastic properties of the layers. To establish a viscoelastic equivalence of the CLT, the correspondence principle [17] has been used. Initially introduced on homogeneous materials, this principle has been extended to heterogeneous and composite materials by Hashin [19]. For a sinusoidal steady-state excitation, in order to convert elastic properties in viscoelastic ones, appropriate complex-plane variables replace the elastic quantities. The laminate's relations derived from CLT are then used to predict general laminate dissipative properties based on the elementary ply properties. The constitutive equation of a laminated plate, which

connects the forces flow (N^*) and bending momentum (M^*) to strains (ε^*) and curvatures (κ^*) is expressed in Eq. 6.

$$\begin{bmatrix} N^*(\omega) \\ M^*(\omega) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A^*(\omega) & B^*(\omega) \\ B^*(\omega) & D^*(\omega) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon^*(\omega) \\ \kappa^*(\omega) \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The complex laminate stiffness matrix ($[ABD]^*$) is calculated from the reduced stiffness matrix (\bar{Q}^*), where h_n represents the n^{th} ply thickness (Eq. 7, 8 and 9).

$$A_{ij}^*(\omega) = A_{ij}'(\omega) + jA_{ij}''(\omega) = \sum_{n=1}^N [\bar{Q}_{ij}^*(\omega)]_n (h_n - h_{n-1}) \quad (7)$$

$$B_{ij}^*(\omega) = B_{ij}'(\omega) + jB_{ij}''(\omega) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^N [\bar{Q}_{ij}^*(\omega)]_n (h_n^2 - h_{n-1}^2) \quad (8)$$

$$D_{ij}^*(\omega) = D_{ij}'(\omega) + jD_{ij}''(\omega) = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{n=1}^N [\bar{Q}_{ij}^*(\omega)]_n (h_n^3 - h_{n-1}^3) \quad (9)$$

\bar{Q}^* is determined using conventional tensor transformations and unidirectional material characteristics (Eq. 10, 11, 12 and 13).

$$Q_{11}^*(\omega) = \frac{E_L^*(\omega)}{(1 - \nu_{TL}\nu_{LT})} = \frac{E_L'(\omega)[1 + j\eta_L(\omega)]}{(1 - \nu_{TL}\nu_{LT})} \quad (10)$$

$$Q_{22}^*(\omega) = \frac{E_T^*(\omega)}{(1 - \nu_{TL}\nu_{LT})} = \frac{E_T'(\omega)[1 + j\eta_T(\omega)]}{(1 - \nu_{TL}\nu_{LT})} \quad (11)$$

$$Q_{12}^*(\omega) = \frac{\nu_{LT}E_T^*(\omega)}{(1 - \nu_{TL}\nu_{LT})} = \frac{\nu_{LT}E_T'(\omega)[1 + j\eta_T(\omega)]}{(1 - \nu_{TL}\nu_{LT})} \quad (12)$$

$$Q_{66}^*(\omega) = G_{LT}^*(\omega) = G_{LT}'(\omega)[1 + j\eta_{LT}(\omega)] \quad (13)$$

The subscripts L and T refer respectively to the longitudinal and transverse directions. G'_{LT} is the ply shear modulus. The major Poisson's ratio (ν_{LT}) is measured from quasi-static tensile test on $[0]_4$ specimens (Eq. 14).

$$\nu_{LT} = -\frac{\varepsilon_T}{\varepsilon_L} \quad (14)$$

In a similar manner, the minor Poisson's ratio (ν_{TL}) can be determined from a simple tensile test where the loading axis of the test specimen is taken perpendicular to the fibre direction of the lamina.

$$\nu_{TL} = -\frac{\varepsilon_L}{\varepsilon_T} \quad (15)$$

The apparent complex longitudinal bending modulus ($E_{app}^*(\omega)$) is then calculated on $[0/90]_s$ specimen by Eq. 16 [20] and compared to the experimental results. The loss factor ($\eta_{app}^*(\omega)$) is then given by the ratio of the imaginary and the real parts of the complex apparent flexural modulus (Eq. 17).

$$E_{app}^*(\omega) = \frac{12}{h^3 D_{11}^{*-1}(\omega)} \quad (16)$$

$$\eta_{app}^*(\omega) = \frac{E''(\omega)}{E'(\omega)} \quad (17)$$

3 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The composite materials have been fabricated by thermo-moulding of unidirectional flax fibres of 150 g/mm² supplied by BioRenforts and an epoxy resin SR8200 from Sicomin. Plates with 4 layers were thermo-compressed under 7 bars and at 60°C during 8 hours. The fibre volume content was of 45%.

As reported in [5], the transverse shear can affect the damping prediction when the length/thickness ratio of the specimens is lower than 100. Therefore, rectangular shaped coupons of 170 mm and 10 mm, with a thickness of 1.05 mm were dry cut from plates. First, [0]₄, [90]₄ and [±45]_s samples have been tested at 23±2°C and 50±3% relative humidity, by vibration analysis to measure the elementary ply viscoelastic properties. Second, [0/90]_s and [±60]_s specimens have been tested. Finally, the predictive method previously described was applied and compared to experimental measurements.

Oberst method is classically used to characterise materials' vibrational behaviour. An electrical inductor generates the excitation of ferromagnetic samples (figure 3a). For non-ferromagnetic materials, a small ferromagnetic chip is bonded on the sample's surface. A modified Oberst device, allowing the characterisation on a large frequency bandwidth of slender beams, has been designed by Wojtowicki et al. [21].

Figure 3: (a) Oberst device for a non-ferromagnetic sample; (b) Oberst-modified experimental device.

In order to avoid the drilling of the specimen on its centre, a bolted aluminium tab has been designed to clamp the beam to the shaft of the shaker (figure 3b). The clamping torque was of 11 N.m. The shaker generates harmonic excitation on the clamped-free beam specimen. A spectrum analyser calculates the Frequency Response Functions (FRF) between the end of the beam velocity and the centre-beam acceleration. A swept-sine excitation, with low variation was applied to the specimen in order to have a locally stationary excitation. The frequency resolution was adjusted to obtain a constant frequency resolution of 30 mHz. The dynamic bandwidth of the test has been fixed between 10 to 4000 Hz. Using relations from beam theory and FRF analyses, E' and η have been calculated by Eq. 18 and 19.

$$E'(\omega_r) = \frac{\rho S \omega_r^2}{\beta^4 I} \quad (18)$$

$$\eta(\omega_r) = \frac{\omega_{r2} - \omega_{r1}}{\omega_r} \quad (19)$$

ω_r is the resonance angular frequency, S is the beam section, ρ is the material density, I is the area moment of inertia, β is a constant depending on the mode. ω_{r2} and ω_{r1} are the angular frequencies at -3dB of magnitude from the peak resonance frequency.

4 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

In order to be consistent with the linear viscoelastic theory, the excitation range has been assessed to ensure a linear ply behaviour. To do so, the mechanical response has been measured for different mode magnitudes. The strain energy (W_s) (Eq. 20) injected on the beam has been calculated from the deflection $v(x,t)$ along the beam length (L) i.e. x direction. E' and η measurements were then analysed for different strain energies (figure 4).

$$W_s = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L EI \left(\frac{\partial^2 v(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 dx \quad (20)$$

Typically, at low strain energy, the material response was independent of the excitation level. The linear responses were measured at low excitation. In order to identify the non-linear threshold, the responses were normalized by the linear value. As plotted in figure 4, it can be noted that, independently of the frequency, the response changed with the strain energy increase. The non-linear threshold has been identified at 5.10^{-6} J, 1.10^{-5} J and 9.10^{-5} J for respectively $[0]_4$, $[90]_4$ and $[\pm 45]_s$ samples. Finally, the specimens' characterisation has been performed under these levels to ensure the linearity of the behaviour.

Figure 4: Non-linearity threshold identification of E_{45} and η_{45} on $[\pm 45]_s$ specimens.

4 IDENTIFICATION

$E'(\omega)$ and $\eta(\omega)$ have been evaluated for the three principal laminate's directions. The results plotted on figure 5-7, were averaged from 4 repetitions, with standard deviation bars. The coefficients of variation, defined as the percentage ratio of the standard deviation and the mean value, were evaluated at each modal frequency. The results have shown a satisfactory variability, lower than 7% for $E'(\omega)$ and $\eta(\omega)$. This variability can be due to the natural scattering of flax fibres but also to the symmetrical positioning of the sample in the test setup.

The linear viscoelastic parameters' have been optimised by least squares method algorithm from Matlab©. The optimisation procedure was separately applied to determine the four parameters (E_1 , E_2 , μ and α) of $E_L^*(\omega)$, $E_T^*(\omega)$ and $E_{45}^*(\omega)$ complex moduli. In the three cases, the iterative procedure consisted in minimizing the difference between experimental and theoretical values, calculated from Eq. 4 and 5. The three sets of parameters obtained are given in table 1. The laminate constitutive relation (Eq. 6) was then implemented on a CLT calculation routine.

Ply linear viscoelastic moduli	E_L^*	E_T^*	E_{45}^*
E_1 (GPa)	18.8	4,63	6,38
E_2 (GPa)	1.49	3.16	0.442
μ (Pa.s)	173 000	15.3	181 000
α	0.370	0,177	0,512

Table 1: Identified parameters of on-axis fractional derivative Zener models

To validate the experimental-numerical method for a general laminate, the storage moduli and loss factors have been measured on a $[90/0]_s$ and $[\pm 60]_s$ specimens. Both CLT

calculation and experimental results are plotted in figure 8 and 9. ν_{LT} and ν_{TL} supposed to be frequency independent, have been respectively identified equal to 0.4 and 0.01.

Figure 5: Experimental and analytical frequency dependence of $E_L'(\omega)$ and $\eta_L(\omega)$ from $[0]_4$ specimens.

Figure 6: Experimental and analytical frequency dependence of $E_T'(\omega)$ and $\eta_T(\omega)$ from $[90]_4$ specimens.

Figure 7: Experimental and analytical frequency dependence of $E_{45}'(\omega)$ and $\eta_{45}(\omega)$ from $[\pm 45]_s$ specimens

4 DISCUSSION

The results have revealed the material's dependence to frequency. When the mode rank increased, storage moduli increased on average by 10 to 16%, as well as loss factors increased by 38 to 56%. Both storage and loss moduli have been identified by Zener model within 700 to 4000 Hz range.

The use of the correspondence principle through the CLT equation has been validated on two biaxial laminates i.e. $[0/90]_s$ and $[\pm 60]_s$ (figure 8 and 9). The comparison between results and simulation showed an accurate prediction of the laminate behaviour with a difference lower than 5% for the loss factor and the storage modulus, within 200 to 4000 Hz bandwidth.

Figure 8: Experimental and analytical prediction on a $[0/90]_s$ biaxial flax/epoxy laminate.

Figure 9: Experimental and analytical prediction on a $[\pm 60]_s$ biaxial flax/epoxy laminate.

The fractional derivative Zener model of linear viscoelasticity has been successfully used to calculate the frequency dependence within 700 to 4000 Hz (figure 5-7). The accuracy of the identification method could be improved by the extension of the characterisation and modelling range to lower and higher frequencies. In addition, the modelling improvement should be achieved through a new equations, considering multiple time relaxation mechanisms such as Wiechert model [17].

The experimental improvement can be reached through tests in temperature and extrapolation with frequency-temperature superposition principle. Usually adopted in isotropic

polymers, this principle can however present some difficulties with multi-phased organic materials [22]. Furthermore, the current experimental-numerical approach could be extended by the use of complex Poisson's ratios. In this case, off-axis laminates' behaviour involving important in-plane shear stress could be more properly predicted. However, this achievement requires biaxial strain measurements attainable with a 3-D scanning vibrometer or dynamic strain gages.

9 CONCLUSION

This study proposed an experimental-numerical method to predict the viscoelastic properties of a general flax fibre laminate. The characterisation method allowed the measurement of moduli and loss factor of unidirectional composite beams in a large band frequency (10 - 4000 Hz). In this range, the storage moduli increased by 10 to 16% and the loss factor by 38 to 56%. The Fractional derivative Zener models identified in the in-plane directions, described the frequency evolution of both moduli and loss factors. Based on the elastic-viscoelastic correspondence principle, classical laminates theory has been successfully used to predict general linear viscoelastic behaviours, validated on $[0/90]_s$ and $[\pm 60]_s$ composite laminae. The results showed an accurate prediction of the laminate loss factor and storage modulus frequency evolution with an average error lower than 5%.

REFERENCES

- [1] Liang S, Gning P B, Guillaumat L. "A comparative study of fatigue behaviour of flax/epoxy and glass/epoxy composites". *Composites Science and Technology*, 2012, 72(5), 535-543.
- [2] Duc F, Bourban P E, Plummer C J G. "Damping of thermoset and thermoplastic flax fibre composites". *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 2014, vol. 64, p. 115-123.
- [3] Rozite L., Joffe R., Varna J. "Characterization and modeling of performance of Polymer Composites Reinforced with Highly Non-Linear Cellulosic Fibers.", *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*. IOP Publishing, 2012. p. 012005.
- [4] Berthelot J.-M., Sefrani Y. "Damping analysis of unidirectional glass and Kevlar fibre composites", *Composites Science and Technology*, 2004, vol. 64, no 9, p. 1261-1278.
- [5] Yim J. H., Gillespie Jr, J. W., "Damping characteristics of 0 and 90 AS4/3501-6 unidirectional laminates including the transverse shear effect", *Composite Structures*, 2000, vol. 50, no 3, p. 217-225.
- [6] Ni R. G., Adams R. D. "The damping and dynamic moduli of symmetric laminated composite beams—theoretical and experimental results", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1984, vol. 18, no 2, p. 104-121.
- [7] Kumar P., Chandra R., Singh S. P., "Measurement of Damping of Fiber Reinforced Composite Material", *Journal of Materials Science and Engineering B*, 2011, vol. 1, no 5, p. 555-564.
- [8] Schultz A. B., Tsai S. W., "Measurements of complex dynamic moduli for laminated fiber-reinforced composites", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1969, vol. 3, no 3, p. 434-443.
- [9] Crane, R. M., Gillespie JR, J. W. Characterization of the vibration damping loss factor of glass and graphite fiber composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, 1991, vol. 40, no 4, p. 355-375.
- [10] Akay M., "Aspects of dynamic mechanical analysis in polymeric composites", *Composites Science and Technology*, 1993, vol. 47, no 4, p. 419-423.
- [11] Melo J. D. D., Radford D. W., "Time and temperature dependence of the viscoelastic properties of CFRP by dynamic mechanical analysis", *Composite Structures*, 2005, vol. 70, no 2, p. 240-253.
- [12] Crane R. M., Gillespie J. W. Jr., "Analytical model for prediction of the damping loss factor of composite materials", *Polymer Composites*, 1992, vol. 13, Issue 3, pages 179-190.
- [13] Lou Y. C., Schapery R. A., "Viscoelastic characterization of a nonlinear fiber-reinforced plastic", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1971, vol. 5, no 2, p. 208-234.

- [14] Gamby D., Lafarie-Frenot M. C., Vinet A., et al. The prediction of the long-term mechanical behaviour of aeronautical laminates. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2001, vol. 61, no 3, p. 439-443.
- [15] Megnis M., Varna J., “Nonlinear viscoelastic, viscoplastic characterization of unidirectional GF/EP composite”, *Mechanics of Time-Dependent Materials*, 2003, vol. 7, no 3-4, p. 269-290.
- [16] Berthe J., Brieu M., Deletombe E. Improved viscoelastic model for laminate composite under static and dynamic loadings. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 2012, p. 0021998312451294
- [17] Tschoegl N. W., “The phenomenological theory of linear viscoelastic behaviour: an introduction”, Berlin: Springer-Verlag, 1989, ISBN-13:978-3-642-73604-9.
- [18] Pritz T. “Analysis of four-parameter fractional derivative model of real solid materials”, *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 1996, vol. 195, no 1, p. 103-115.
- [19] Hashin Z., “Complex moduli of viscoelastic composites — II. Fiber reinforced materials”, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 1970, vol. 6, n°6, p. 797-807.
- [20] Berthelot J-M. « Matériaux composites: comportement mécanique et analyse des structures ». Tec & doc, 1999.
- [21] Wojtowicki J-L., Jaouen L., Panneton R., “New approach for the measurement of damping properties of materials using the Oberst beam”, *Review of Scientific Instruments* 75, 2004, vol. 75, no 8, p. 2569-2574.
- [22] Fesko D. G., Tschoegl N. W. “Time-temperature superposition in thermorheologically complex materials”, *Journal of Polymer Science Part C: Polymer Symposia*, 1971. p. 51-69.